

CONCEPT-DIABETES DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN TO ANALYSE HEALTHCARE PATHWAYS OF TYPE 2 DIABETES

Version 0

Description

This publication corresponds to the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Baseline Use Case proposed in the CONCEPT-DIABETES project for the implementation of a federated network analysis of the healthcare pathway of type 2 diabetes, version v0.2.0.

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Researchers

ENRIQUE BERNAL-DELGADO (orcid:0000-0002-0961-3298),
Javier Gorricho (orcid:0000-0003-3609-9922), Oscar Lecea
(orcid:0000-0001-7479-1528), Natalia Martínez-Lizaga
(orcid:0000-0002-9586-7955), Ibai Tamayo (orcid:0000-0003-
2860-3359), Francisco Estupiñán Romero (orcid:0000-0002-
6285-8120), Conchi Moreno Iribas (orcid:0000-0001-6537-
0131), LLUÍS FORGA (orcid:0000-0001-7789-133X), Asier
Ballesteros Domínguez (orcid:0000-0002-2195-4669), Maria
Jose Goñi Iriarte (orcid:0000-0002-9239-657X), Daniel

Bejarano-Quisoboni (orcid:0000-0003-2721-2700), Lidia García-Pérez (orcid:0000-0002-5626-8116), Berta Ibáñez (orcid:0000-0002-7797-4845), Ignacio Oscoz (orcid:0009-0004-0387-6056), Sara Trujillo-Alemán (orcid:0000-0002-6508-5768), Cristina Valcárcel-Nazco (orcid:0000-0003-4833-7967), Isabel Hurtado (orcid:0000-0002-8475-8112), Mónica Enguita-Germán (orcid:0000-0002-2890-1252), Javier González Galindo (orcid:0000-0002-8783-5478), Javier Lafita Labacena (orcid:0000-0003-1711-2466), Eduardo Millán (orcid:0000-0002-9688-9304), Julian Librero (orcid:0000-0002-4859-9054), Ester Angulo-Pueyo (orcid:0000-0001-7442-3450), Naiara Parraza Diez (orcid:0000-0002-5902-0351)

Organizations

Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud, Navarrabiomed

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: **CONCEPT-DIABETES DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN TO ANALYSE HEALTHCARE PATHWAYS OF TYPE 2 DIABETES**

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ENRIQUE BERNAL-DELGADO (orcid:0000-0002-0961-3298)
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Navarrabiomed

Contact: Berta Ibáñez

2. Funding

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3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

CONCEPT-DIABETES DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN TO ANALYSE HEALTHCARE PATHWAYS OF TYPE 2 DIABETES

The CONCEPT-DIABETES project aims to analyse chronic care effectiveness and efficiency of care pathways in diabetes, assuming the relevance of care pathways as independent factors of health outcomes using data from real life world (RWD) from five Spanish Regional Health System.

The study protocol is available in <https://zenodo.org/records/10958692>

The data model is available in <https://zenodo.org/records/7778291>

Data is provided pseudonymised and in compliance with the baseline use case data model specification by BARDENA and granted by the Ethical Research Committee of Navarra (Project 97/2019, August 28, 2019).

The CONCEPT-DIABETES project allows to analyze data obtained from all patients with code of Type 2 Diabetes in the clinical health records of five regional health services of Spain: Navarre, Aragon, Basque Country, Valencia and Canary Islands using a decentraized structure via dockers, in a way that there is no need to share the datasets among partners, which facilitate reproducibility.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The analysis requires the secondary use of pseudonymised individual-level data from Health Electronic Records or mortality. Databases include patient administrative information, clinical information from primary care and from

specialized care, data from CMBD (hospital admissions), prescription of drugs and mortality.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

The retrospective analysis will be based on Observational data of routinely collected information from healthcare and public health information systems in five autonomous communities (Spain).

1.1.5 What is its format?

Comma Separated Values (*.csv)

The separator symbol is 'comma'. See datamodel specifications in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7778291>, where synthetic data are given.

The analysis will be performed in a federated maner maintaining pseudonimized individual level data "Within the system".

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Order of 5-50 Gigabytes

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To make informed decisions

The data is expected to respond to the following research questions:

- What are the care pathways that patients with type 2 diabetes follow within the health system?
- Do the care pathways match with the international recommendations and clinical guidelines?

- Does the adherence to the clinical guidelines affect the outcomes of the patients in terms of control of the disease and complications?
- Does process mining methodology improve the prediction performance of health outcomes (included cardiovascular events) over traditional analytical methods?

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The original data sources for Navarra are the mortality register, the population register, and BARDENA, which is a population data warehouse of the Navarre Health Department that integrates individual-level information generated at any level of health of approximately 97% of the Navarre population. BARDENA contains information from the CMBD (hospital admissions), from Primary Care and from Specialized Care.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy

The analysis of the care pathways in patients with Type 2 Diabetes (T2D), represented as the sequence of events that a patient experiences with the health system in the evolution of the disease, is a valuable information for policy makers, endocrinologist, primary care professionals and Clinical Guidelines designers. It allows to visualize the real pathways of the patients, to measure the distance from them to the theoretical pathways and also to identify if this distance is related with health outcomes.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Further information regarding cohort definition is published in [CONCEPT-DIABETES DATA MODEL TO ANALYSE HEALTHCARE PATHWAYS OF TYPE 2 DIABETES](#) (DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8093865), including metadata information, data schema and synthetic data set complying with the common data model specifications.

All researchers authoring and contributing to the study are referenced by their ORCID.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Image 1

Complete metadata, in human and machine readable formats are provided at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8093865>:

CONCEPT-DIABETES datamodel specification in *.xlsx format. -Human-readable version (Excel)-

CONCEPT-DIABETES datamodel specification EXPLANATION in *.pptx format. -Human-readable version (PowerPoint)-

Case use and software for data analysis are provided in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10043569>:

CONCEPT-DIABETES data model rule sets *.json - Machine-readable version-

CONCEPT-DIABETES data model analytical pipeline *.html -Human-readable version -

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural
- Reference

Published Metadata includes:

- **Administrative information** on the Project name, Project URL, Use case, Type of document, Version (SEM), Authors, Contributors, General Description of the project, and data model change log.

- **Cohort definition**, including cohort description, inclusion and exclusion criteria, and study period.

- **Individual-level information requirements**, including model entities:

- **Variable syntactic information:** variable label, variable description (concept), encoding, variable format, variable type, units, requirement level (required/recommended/optional), variable validation rules, transformations at origin, variable property, possible data source(s), and comments

- entity/variable semantic definition, including entity name, entity description, entity definition, other specifications,

- crosswalks, including: classifications system (international or national standard classifications for diseases, procedures or drugs), code, clean code (code without special characters), code description,- source of the code, and other observations on the code

- Other administrative information published regarding the original data's geographical, population and time coverage of the expected data input is provided in the same publication as additional information

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

ISO 8601 (dates), ISO 3166-1(countries), CIAP2 (BDCAP), ICD10,WHO-ATC/DDD Index

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

Any date using ISO 8601

Countries using ISO 3166-1

Any comorbidity/hospital admission codes using CIAP2 (BDCAP), ICD10

Any diagnostic using ICD10

Any procedure using ICD10

Any drug using WHO-ATC/DDD Index 2023

See details in datamodel description
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7778291>, in
Datamodel_CONCEPT_DM2_explanation.pptx document.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

health services research, national health programs, healthcare disparities,
Process Mining, quality of health care, common data model, CONCEPT

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

The datamodel is in JSON format, so it is machine-readable

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The datasets will not be deposited in an online repository, neither shared between partners. They will be stored in the secure server of each Regional Public Health System of the communities that participate in the study. The work scheme will be with a de-centralized infrastructure. Metadata, synthetic data, pipelines and outputs will be published in ZENODO, and results of each specific aim in open access journals.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

None

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

CONCEPT- DM2 DATA MODEL TO ANALYSE HEALTHCARE PATHWAYS OF TYPE 2 DIABETES

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

Patient level data is never shared across partners. The federated nature of the framework allows for metaanalysis given data structures are maintained across communities.

Thus, only fully aggregated non-sensitive results (obtained after deploying the analysis pipeline) will be exported from the secure processing environment (SPE).

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Individual level data is limited in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Additionally, the individual-level datasets generated or analyzed during the current study do not fulfill the requirements for open data access. The data is too dense and comprehensive to preserve patient privacy.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

The datamodel can be accessed in Zenodo. The outputs will be accessed making use of dockerized virtual machines developed and shared within the framework developers.

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

There is no need of any method to access the dataset/output. Outputs will be in zenodo. To conduct the analysis in another dataset, the data will be loaded and analyzed using Docker (Hypervirtualize).

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

The protocol of the CONCEPT-DIABETES project was approved by the medical ethics committees of each autonomous comitee August/2019.

No sensitive data will be shared outside the secured environment of each regional organization.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Data within the secured environment can only be accessed by authorized users to produce the expected results of analyses planned within the study protocol following the research project's purposes, scope and objectives.

Aggregated non-sensitive data outputs of the analysis will be published under open licenses as research outputs/outcomes at any time during or after the project's completion.

See 3.2.2.6

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Aggregated data outputs and other outputs of the analysis can (or must) be published under open licenses as research outputs/outcomes at any time during or after the project's completion. However, individual level (and locally accessible data) will be stored between 5 and 15 years (according to each regional health data policies in agreement of the law for Biomedical research).

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

See the information provided in section 3.1. The data model is given in <https://zenodo.org/records/7778291>.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Information on the data access process, data request procedure and data access are provided as part of this Data Management Plan (DMP).

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

The common data model is published under an open license (CC BY 4.0 International) in Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/records/7778291>

This DMP will be published under an open license (CC BY 4.0 International) in Zenodo and will be updated during the project.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

A GitHub repository linked to the Zenodo publication of the data model to develop the quality check exploratory data analyses and database generation following the specifications of the data model has been set up.

<https://github.com/metodologianavarrabiomed/CONCEPT-DIABETES>

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

We follow the general best practices and approach provided by the European Interoperability Framework (EIF)

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The study protocol has a qualified reference ('requires') with the common data model specification both published in Zenodo.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

All publications are under a CC BY 4.0 license
(<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>)

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

- Other

Other: We use Standardized Ejecution Environment with Docker.

Other: We also share the Quality check exploratory anlyses, missing data imputation, process discovery and prediction algorithms.

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

We intend to ensure the use of the project outputs (including aggregated data) by third parties after the end of the project.

We will not share or publish any original individual-level data as this is subject to all restrictions within the data access request and national and international data protection regulations.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The provenance of the original data is well-documented in the study protocol and the current DMP, although not fully documented in the published metadata.

We only include as provenance information some information on the authors of the study and data managers of the original dataset regarding their names, contact information, affiliation (i.e. institution) and some information on the source of data provided within the context of the CONCEPT project framework. Most information comes from BARDENA, which has been described in

Gorricho J, Leache L, Tamayo I, et al. Data Resource Profile: Results Analysis Base of Navarre (BARDENA). *Int J Epidemiol.* 2023;52(6):e301-e307.
doi:10.1093/ije/dyad144

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

We have implemented our own data quality assessment and assurance procedures within the CONCEPT framework, aiming to provide insight into the impact of data quality in interpreting the research outcomes and producing high-quality research. Those procedures include the assessment of the information requirements and the data model specification by a scientific and technical committee, the implementation of an automatic data quality check on the original dataset (linked and transformed data to comply with the requirements captured in the common data model specification, conditional on data availability and access) of each participating node, the implementation of data conformance and consistency checking following the common data model specification, and a final missing values assessment on core variables to inform decisions on imputation requirements. Additionally, algorithms of process discovery and prediction are also shared.

Each quality assessment, checking and analytical procedure is performed within the secured processing environment (SPE) of each participating node.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Re-use
- Security
- Other

0

Direct cost

Extraction of data from sources is not free in some of the participant regions. However, the output of the analyses will be FAIR at no cost.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure
- Other

Data extraction cost was included in the budget of the project (approximately 2500 € per region), dependent on National funding.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Ignacio Oscoz (orcid:0009-0004-0387-6056)

Software management and data analysis (Navarra)

b. Asier Ballesteros Domínguez (orcid:0000-0002-2195-4669)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data Management and data analysis (Navarra)

c. Javier González Galindo (orcid:0000-0002-8783-5478)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data Management (pipelines Aragon)

d. Natalia Martínez-Lizaga (orcid:0000-0002-9586-7955)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data Management (Aragon)

e. Eduardo Millán (orcid:0000-0002-9688-9304)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data Management (Basque Country)

f. Conchi Moreno Iribas (orcid:0000-0001-6537-0131)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data management (mortality register, Navarra)

g. Sara Trujillo-Alemán (orcid:0000-0002-6508-5768)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data Management (Canarias Islands)

h. Javier Gorricho (orcid:0000-0003-3609-9922)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data management (BARDENA Navarra)

i. Laura Arnedo Ajona (orcid:0000-0003-2329-3267)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data management (Navarra - population register)

j. Berta Ibáñez (orcid:0000-0002-7797-4845)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Data Scientist. Coordinator (Navarra)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

Original data is de-identified and pseudonymised before being given to the researchers. An EIPD (evaluation of impact in data protection) was conducted by the Principal Researcher, with the help of the Data Protection Delegate of Navarrabiomed. All data of the different autonomous communities will be password protected and be hosted locally only in machines inside the secured environment of the governments intranet following safety protocols of each government's policies.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

Data will be accessed exclusively by the research technicians involved in the analysis in each autonomous community. Only aggregated results will be shared between project partners.

Researchers are responsible for complying with data access conditions and data protection and privacy regulation.

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Pseudonymized data will be stored locally. Complying with the organic Law on Data Protection, weighted by the Biomedical Research Act, the data will be stored not less than 5 years after finalization of the CONCEPT-Diabetes project, and fully erased after 15 years.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Individual-level data can not be shared as it is considered highly sensitive even after de-identification, pseudonymization and minimization.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Privacy policies
- National laws

- Other

See descriptions of data processing and data access in section 3.2.2

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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